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Current status of NEDO project on durability and reliability of SOFC cell-stacks

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Abstract

The Japanese national R&D project on SOFC durability and reliability has been conducting by the New Energy Development Organization (NEDO) for more than 10 years. The current project focused on the elucidation of the degradation mechanism for the rapid evaluation method of a lifetime of 10 years (90,000 hours). Until 2017, we have completed the evaluation methods for the lifetime of stacks by the elucidation of the degradation mechanisms. From 2018 to 2019, the project was extended for focusing on the improvement of the efficiency of SOFC cell-stacks. The target of the project is the following: (1) to make a concept for high efficient SOFC cell-stack over 65%LHV and (2) to make a concept of toughness on cell-stacks with load cycling. This paper reports recent achievements on the concepts for high efficiency and load cycling of stacks in 2018-2019. Some cell-stacks showed relatively high stability against high fuel utilization over $U_f=80\%$: the degradation rate was about 0.3-2.0 %/kh, which is the same level of normal condition. The post analyses were examined at the samples with high U_f operation. In the stacks operated at high U_f , Ni oxidation and microstructure change were observed at Ni-YSZ anode. The feasibility study on high efficiency and load cycling of stacks suggested the possibility and limitation of stacks that operated at high efficient modes.

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Introduction

The Japanese national R&D project on SOFC durability and reliability has been conducting by the New Energy Development Organization (NEDO) for more than 10 years [1-3]. A recent project is “Technology Development for Promotion of Practical Application of Solid Oxide Fuel Cells (FY 2013- 2019)”, in which much efforts were focused on the elucidation of degradation mechanism and the development of evaluation method of the lifetime of cell-stacks (Fig.1). During the first term of the project (2013-2017), the rapid evaluation methods of durability were developed to evaluate the lifetime with 10 years (90,000 hours) [4]. The Central Research Institute for Electric Power Industries (CRIEPI) developed the current interruption methods for the evaluation of resistance arising from the stacks with electrode polarization and ohmic resistances. Several universities and research institutes proposed the advanced evaluation methods for degradation of cell-stacks, such as impurity concentration at the electrode/electrolyte interfaces (AIST), 3D-reconstruction and microstructure change evaluation methods with FIB-SEM/STEM (Kyoto Univ., Univ. Tokyo, and Kyushu University), stress and mechanical strength evaluation under operation condition (Tohoku Univ.), and simulation methods of electrode-cell-stack performances (Kyoto Univ., Univ. Tokyo, Tohoku Univ., and AIST). From 2018, according to the Japanese Basic Hydrogen Plan for promoting the higher efficiency and wider application of fuel cells by the Japanese government [5, 6], we started the feasibility study of SOFC stacks durability with high-efficient and load cycling modes [7,8]. In this paper, the progress of the project is reported especially on the feasibility of stack durability at high efficiency (LHV 65% concept) and load cycling in 2018-2019.

Figure 1 History of national project on SOFC durability and improvement of degradation rates.

Project structure and member

Figure 2 shows a structure of the recent project for the development of the concept with high-efficient/toughness cell-stacks. The project is composed of four research sub-projects: 1) Stack durability evaluation, 2) Clarification of degradation mechanism, 3) Evaluation methods development, and 4) Integration and Summary. The sub-project is correlated with each other for promoting the R&D and to accomplish the target. On the left-hand side, several cell-stack developers (KYOCERA Corporation Ltd., NGK-Insulators Co., Ltd., MORIMURA SOFC TECHNOLOGY Co., LTD, and DENSO CORPORATION) supplied their stacks to the CRIEPI for the evaluation of degradation in the long-term operation at high fuel utilization over 80% and load cycling. Other topics were conducted by a collaboration with some companies and universities/ research institutes. On the right-hand side, the degradation mechanism was investigated at the academic consortium (universities and research institute) by using their superior analytical techniques.

Figure 2 Schematic diagram of the project structure of “Fundamental study for Rapid Evaluation Method of SOFC Durability (2018-2019).”

(MORIMURA SOFC TECHNOLOGY CO., LTD: inherited Planer SOFC business from NGK sparkplug from 2019)

Stack durability test under high efficiency

The long-term operation tests with relatively high fuel utilization have been conducted for four practical stacks. Table 1 summarizes the degradation rates and degradation factors of stacks over ten thousand hours' operation measured by CRIEPI. The degradation rates of flat-tube (KYOCERA Corporation), segment in-series (NGK Insulators), planer (MORIMURA SOFC TECHNOLOGY Co., LTD), and planer (DENSO Corporation) are examined between the high ($U_f=80$ and 85%) and normal ($U_f\sim 70\%$) fuel utilizations. The degradation rates at high fuel utilization are similar values between high and normal, indicating high stability under high fuel utilization examined. The main degradation factor of these stacks is an increase of resistance at the ohmic and the polarization of cathode, which is the same increase trends under the normal fuel utilization conditions. With increasing fuel utilization up to 85%, the stack degradation gradually increased in the flat tubular stacks, while the degradation rates of segment in-series and planer show the same level with $U_f=80\%$. Even high fuel utilization at $U_f=85\%$, the degradation factors were the same with $U_f=80\%$, which indicates a similar degradation mechanism occurred in the stacks. The degradation rates were also examined at several kinds of load cycling (power output fluctuation). The precise experimental results will be given in another paper elsewhere. The degradation by load cycling is relatively small with almost no difference in the degradation rates with the normal steady-state operation. The experimental results suggest that the possibility of high efficiency operation of the present cell-stacks, although microstructures of cells can be damaged at the nano-micrometer level of Ni-YSZ anode and cathode.

Table 1. Degradation rates and factors of several stacks under high fuel utilization (measured by CRIEPI) (Report from NEDO Project (2020)).

Fuel utilization, U_f		Flat tubular (KYOCERA Co.)	Segment in-series (NGK Insulators)	Planer (MORIMURA SOFC TECH.)	Planer (DENSO Co.)
$U_f=80\%$	Test of duration	11,348 h	12,100 h	18,815 h	5,477 h
	Degradation rate	0.34%/kh	0.46%/kh	0.31%/kh	2.85%/kh
	Main deg. factors	IR-loss, Cathode	IR-loss	IR-loss, Cathode	Cathode
$U_f\sim 70\%$ reference	Deg.rate	0.33%/kh	0.49%/kh	0.34%/kh	$\sim 2.0\%/kh$
$U_f=85\%$	Test of duration	6,899 h	7,760 h	9,030 h	No data
	Degradation rate	- 0.51%/1kh	- 0.52%/1kh	0.38%/1kh	No data
	Main deg. factors	IR-loss, Cathode	IR-loss	IR-loss, Cathode	No data

Post Analysis of cell-stacks operated at high fuel utilization

The post analyses of cell-stacks after the high fuel utilization/load cycling tests were examined by the academic institutes (Universities and AIST). In this report, part of the obtained results is presented at Ni-YSZ anode of the flat-tube and planer stacks. Figure 3 shows an example of microstructures of Ni-YSZ anode/support (distribution of Ni by SEM/EDS) operated after load cycling under normal ($U_f \sim 70\%$) and high ($U_f = 80\%$) fuel utilization. The images are taken at the upper cells (outlet of fuel gases), where much amounts of water vapor exist in the fuel gases (left and middle), with reference at the bottom (left). As shown in Fig.3, no obvious Ni growth was observed at anode and support, suggesting the stability of microstructures in Ni-YSZ under load cycling. Even though the amount of water vapors, the microstructure is kept as the original in the observed areas. This indicates the stability of Ni-YSZ anode under high humidity conditions.

Figure 3 Microstructures of Ni at the Ni-YSZ anode and support: SEM/EDS mapping of Ni (data obtained by AIST, from NEDO project report (2020)).

In the planer type cell-stacks (MORIMURA SOFC TECHNOLOGY Co., LTD.), there is a decrease of TPB length after the operation. Figure 4 shows the volume-specific TPB length of Ni-YSZ anode after the long-term operation of planer cells at the inlet and outlet of fuel gases. The TPB length decreased close to the anode/electrolyte interfaces at the outlet side of the cell, suggesting a significant loss of Ni close to the anode/electrolyte interfaces. Further microstructure analysis suggested that the loss of Ni particles in Ni-YSZ anode by the formation of $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ and NiO due to high water vapor pressures and polarization. This indicates the significant movements of Ni by the diffusion or evaporation in the planer cells: the lower activity of Ni-YSZ anode at the outlet of fuel gases (higher water vapor pressure areas). Therefore, it is very important to evaluate the active areas working as anode under high water vapor pressures for high efficient modes.

Figure 4 Length of TPB close to the anode/electrolyte interfaces by the 3D reconstruction methods (data obtained by Kyoto University, from NEDO project report (2020)).

Summary

The recent SOFC national project of Japan was introduced: NEDO project, “Technology Development for Promoting SOFC Commercialization/ Fundamental study for Rapid Evaluation Method of SOFC Durability (2018-2019)”. In the term of 2018-2019, the target of the project is (1) making a concept for high-efficient SOFC cell-stacks over 65%LHV and (2) making a concept for toughness on cell-stacks with load cycling. Rapid evaluation methods were applied to the samples after the high-efficient operation. The project was successful in making the concept for high efficiency and toughness of SOFC cell-stacks. The cell-stack showed relatively high stability against high fuel utilization (over 80%) and power output changes. By the post-analysis of cell-stacks after high fuel utilization and load cycling, there can be the formation of NiO due to the high water vapor pressures at the outlet of fuel gases in the planer cell-sack. Therefore, we need an optimization of fuel flows in the planer type for the high efficient mode operation. Further investigation is needed to improve the performance of cell-stacks.

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